

Appendix B: Psychometric analysis and validation

A unidimensional Rasch model was estimated under the one-parameter logistic (1PL) framework to analyse the psychometric properties of a set of performance-based items. The analysis focused on items designed to assess a single latent trait, assuming equal discrimination across items and allowing only item difficulty parameters to vary. The estimation procedure converged after 15 iterations, yielding a deviance of 13,528.53. The absolute and relative parameter changes approached zero, indicating model stability. The estimated variance of the latent trait was 0.319, and the empirical reliability coefficient (EAP reliability) reached 0.703, reflecting an expected level of measurement precision.

The distribution of item difficulties ranged from -3.41 to $+2.30$, with a mean of -0.13 and a standard deviation of 1.29. The median item difficulty was approximately zero (0.06), suggesting that the scale was centred near the expected average ability level of the sample. This relatively wide spread of difficulties indicates that the item set effectively captures variation across low to high latent trait levels.

To provide a more interpretable framework for item difficulty, each item was classified based on its logit value in relation to the standard deviation of item difficulty estimates. Following established guidelines, items with logit values greater than $+1.29$ were considered very difficult, those between 0 and $+1.29$ as difficult, those between -1.29 and 0 as easy, and those below -1.29 as very easy. Based on this classification, 13.08% of the items were identified as very difficult, 39.25% as difficult, 26.17% as easy, and 21.50% as very easy. This distribution demonstrates an intentional spread of item difficulties, ensuring that the instrument is capable of discriminating respondents across the full continuum of the latent trait.

The Test Information Curve (TIC) showed (Figure 1) that the test provides the most information—i.e., the greatest measurement precision—around the average ability level ($\theta = 0$). The information decreases symmetrically as ability levels move toward the lower or higher ends of the latent trait continuum. This suggests that the test is most effective at distinguishing individuals with average proficiency and less precise for individuals with very low or very high ability.

Figure 1. Test Information Curve (TIC)

The histograms of Infit (Figure 2) and Outfit (Figure 3) statistics indicated that most items exhibit values close to the expected range of 1.0, with relatively symmetric distributions and limited skewness. Vertical reference lines at 0.7 and 1.3—common thresholds for acceptable fit—suggest that most items fall well within acceptable limits. Consistently, the classification of item fit shows that 100 out of 107 items (93.5%) are considered to adjust adequately to the Rasch model, while only 7 items (6.5%) do not meet the established fit criteria. This supports

the item set's overall integrity and unidimensional structure, suggesting that the scale provides reliable and interpretable measurement across items.

Figure 2. Histogram of Infit Statistics

Figure 3. Histogram of Outfit Statistics

The Person-Item Map (Figure 3) displayed the alignment between the distribution of person abilities and item difficulties along the latent trait continuum (θ). The items are spread across a wide range of difficulty levels, while the person's abilities appear to cluster slightly above the centre of the scale. This suggests that, overall, the item set is reasonably well-targeted to the sample. However, the test may be slightly less informative for individuals at the highest and lowest ends of the ability spectrum.

Person-Item Map (eRm)

Figure 3. Person-Item Map

The distribution of plausible ability values (θ) across the three subscales (Figure 4): Functional, Sociocritical, and Technical, each exhibited a roughly normal distribution, indicating a good spread of abilities among participants. The Functional and Sociocritical subscales appeared slightly skewed toward lower ability levels, while the Technical subscale was more symmetric and sharply peaked, suggesting greater precision around the mean.

Figure 4. Histograms of Plausible Values by Subscale